

Spiral Structure of Cylindrical Batteries and its Importance in Modeling of Heat Transfer

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Extended Abstract

This study investigates the importance of considering the well-known spiral structure of cylindrical batteries in numerical models of heat transfer within the battery. Such models typically simplify the internal geometry by a concentric layout with electrodes and separators. This results in an effective orthotropic thermal conductivity with radial, tangential and axial components defined in a local cylindrical coordinate system [1]. This simplification is likely due to the ease of implementation in standard CFD software, which typically employs cylindrical orthotropic material properties that seem to address the problem at first glance. However, this approach is not entirely accurate and requires careful consideration to ensure that important factors, such as the spiral structure, are not overlooked. This work fills that research gap by presenting a series of numerical simulations that explicitly consider spiral geometry [2].

The computational domain consists of a cylinder with a radius of 9 mm representing an 18650 Li-Ion cell. The Dirichlet boundary condition is set on the outer diameter of a cylinder with a constant wall temperature. A steady state is assumed. This setting can simulate the case when a Li-Ion cell is discharging/charging at a low current and immersed in a phase change material with a melting point close to the Dirichlet boundary condition.

Based on the results of the difference between spiral and circular thermal conductivity, it can be said that the spiral structure is not required in the numerical model as no difference can be observed at all in temperature fields in real geometrical cases. The explanation is that tangential vectors of circles and a spiral at intersection points have almost identical directions for points further than 1 mm from the centre of the battery. On the other hand, for very sparse spirals, a significant error occurs (up to 10 K) due to the very effective heat removal along the spiral to the outside of the battery. Indeed, the thermal conductivity tensor can be assumed to have constant components – radial, tangential and axial, in standard simulations, thus validating the simplifications widely adopted in the literature.

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Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Dataset for article Spiral Structure of Cylindrical Batteries and its Importance in Modeling of Heat Transfer at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14016713>, reference number [2].

References

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